

The Support and Assistance of the Soviet Union and China to Vietnam During the Resistance War Against French Colonialism (1945-1954)

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Abstract

During the resistance war against French colonial invasion, under the strategic leadership of the Communist Party, the Vietnamese people received international support and assistance for their just struggle. Vietnam's resistance war was closely linked to the patriotic wars of the Lao and Cambodian people and aligned with the broader liberation movements of oppressed nations and progressive peoples around the world, aimed at national and social liberation, peace protection, and opposition to aggressive wars, garnered widespread support from the global community – especially from the people of the Soviet Union and China.

Keywords: *Support, assistance, Soviet Union, China, Vietnam's resistance war.*

Suggested citation: Oanh, P.T.K. (2025). The Support and Assistance of the Soviet Union and China to Vietnam During the Resistance War Against French Colonialism (1945-1954). *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 116-123. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(3).11

China's Support for Vietnam in the Fight against French Colonialism

From the early days of the resistance war, even before the establishment of official diplomatic relations, Vietnam had contact with the South Route of the Chinese Eighth Route Army in South China and the Command of the Dian-Gui border region near the Vietnam-China border. In early 1948, president HỒ Chí Minh and the standing committee of the central party welcomed envoys from the Chinese Communist Party to Việt Bắc to exchange information and discuss military coordination along the border. Vietnam provided food, supplies, and weapons to the Dian-Gui border region (Yunnan-Guangxi), coordinated with the Chinese People's Liberation Army to expand the liberated zones in the Việt-Gui border area (Guangdong-Guangxi), and assisted in printing currency.

On October 8, 1949, the Workers' Party of Vietnam sent an official letter to the Communist Party of China, stating: "*Faced with technical difficulties that our current economic conditions do not allow us to overcome, confronted by the urgent need to seize time from the enemy, and the tactical tasks required for transitioning to a new strategic phase, we cannot but request your assistance with weapons, ammunition, equipment, and personnel... For any of the items we request that you are unable to provide, we kindly ask you to forward our request to the Soviet Union and explain our difficulties to our Soviet comrades*" (Trung, 2009). However, in the early period, China's ability to assist the Vietnamese revolution was still limited, as the Chinese revolution had only recently succeeded and the country was facing numerous challenges.

On January 15, 1950, the Democratic Republic of Vietnam officially recognized the People's Republic of China. On January 18, 1950, the People's Republic of China recognized the Democratic Republic of Vietnam.

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After the establishment of diplomatic relations between the two governments, despite China's stagnant and underdeveloped economy and the hardships faced by its people in the aftermath of war, China still provided aid to Vietnam.

At the end of January 1950, president Hồ Chí Minh secretly traveled to China via the Cao Bằng border to meet with Chinese leaders and discuss aid for Vietnam's resistance against the French. In a meeting held in February 1950 in Moscow between president Hồ Chí Minh, Joseph Stalin, and Mao Zedong, chairman Mao affirmed China's commitment to support Vietnam: "*Vietnam needs to equip ten divisions to defeat the French; for now, equip six divisions in the North. Vietnam may immediately send some units to receive weapons on Chinese territory. Guangxi province will serve as Vietnam's direct rear base*" (Giáp, 1999: 15).

In early 1950, right after the two countries established diplomatic relations, president Hồ Chí Minh paid a visit to China, "it was a secret trip... officially, it was a delegation from the central committee of the Party visiting the Chinese Communist Party" (Giáp, 2004: 629). Upon arrival, Hồ Chí Minh met with Liu Shaoqi and Zhu De (at that time, Mao Zedong and Zhou Enlai were in the Soviet Union preparing for the signing of the Sino-Soviet Treaty of Friendship and Alliance) (Dy, 2002: 2).

During the reception, vice chairman Liu Shaoqi said: "*The resistance war in Vietnam, under the leadership of the Vietnamese Party, is justifiable and admirable. The Chinese Party is fully committed to assisting the Vietnamese Party in fulfilling this task*" (Department of Research, Ministry of National Defense, n.d. a: 29) In response to Hồ Chí Minh's request for aid, Liu Shaoqi replied: "*We are determined to support Vietnam's resistance against the French. Once chairman Mao and comrade Zhou Enlai return, the central committee of the Chinese Communist Party will thoroughly review the content and methods of assistance and determine the specifics based on your needs*" (Department of Research, Ministry of National Defense, n.d. b: 18).

In a working meeting with President Hồ Chí Minh (March 1950), Mao Zedong affirmed: "*Vietnam needs to equip ten divisions to defeat the French; for now, equip six divisions currently in the North. Vietnam can immediately send some units to receive weapons on Chinese territory. Guangxi Province will serve as Vietnam's direct rear base*" (Giáp, 1999: 15).

President Hồ Chí Minh proposed that China send an advisory delegation to assist Vietnam. The Chinese side agreed and provided a list of four key leaders: Luo Guibo (La Quý Ba), a member of the Central Committee of the Chinese Communist Party, was appointed as head of the advisory delegation; Wei Guoqing (Vi Quốc Thanh) was appointed chief military advisor; Mei Jiasheng (Mai Gia Sinh) served as advisor for general staff operations; and Ma Xifu (Mã Tây Phu) served as logistics advisor.

According to the agreement, in April 1950, three Vietnamese regiments (from the 308th, 209th, and 174th divisions) went to Mongtu (Yunnan) and East China (Guangxi) to receive weapons and undergo military training in China. Simultaneously, China quickly transported weapons to Cao Bằng to equip two other Vietnamese regiments engaged in fighting on the battlefield.

Thanks to Chinese weapon supplies, the firepower strength of our infantry regiments was completely transformed compared to before. Vietnamese units sent to China not only received weapons but were also trained by the Chinese in assault tactics, especially demolition techniques, which had not been previously used due to lack of explosives. Besides assault tactics, Vietnamese troops also learned "mobile outdoor combat," coordination between infantry and artillery, and tactics such as "siege to attack relief forces," "one point, two sides," and the organization of "four squads, one team."

To ensure logistics and strengthen the transportation of aid materials to Vietnamese troops, on August 6, 1950, the Logistics General Department of the Chinese People's Liberation Army established an office in Nanning. China became a bridge connecting Vietnam with socialist countries and progressive forces worldwide, helping Vietnam receive aid from the Soviet Union and other socialist countries. Guangxi province became the main receiving point for aid to Vietnam and the site for training and developing Vietnamese military officers and technical specialists. China appointed Tran Canh as the Communist Party representative, who, along with the Chinese military advisory group, helped Vietnam launch the Border Campaign. After the victory of the 1950 Border Campaign, the Vietnam-China border route was

opened, allowing more countries the greater opportunity to assist the Vietnamese people, especially the Chinese Communist Party and its people, who provided enormous spiritual and material support and played the primary role in aiding Vietnam. According to Vietnamese official statistics, by the end of 1950, Vietnam had received 3,983 tons of aid from China (General Department of Logistics, 1985: 146)¹, including 1,020 tons of weapons and ammunition (including arms brought back by Vietnamese units trained in China), 161 tons of military supplies, 20 tons of medical drugs and equipment, 71 tons of military goods, 30 Molotov transport vehicles, and 2,634 tons of rice (Military History Institute, 1994: 542)². Although this aid accounted for only 18.5% of the total material used by the Vietnamese army in 1950, it was extremely valuable in the conditions of scarcity at the time, helping equip and increase the combat strength of several key units on the main Northern battlefield. Regarding Chinese aid to Vietnam, researcher François Joyaux further noted: After the Chinese government recognized the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, the first military aid agreement between Vietnam and China was signed in Beijing.

According to this agreement, Beijing would deliver 150,000 rifles confiscated from the Japanese and 10,000 American carbines along with corresponding ammunition. The Việt Minh began receiving these weapons from the spring of 1950 (Joyaux, 1981: 82). Joyaux also noted that, “from this period, the main Viet Minh units (22,000 soldiers) were sent to China for training” (Joyaux, 1981: 83).

In 1950, Vietnam sent some young cadres to study foreign languages and diplomatic skills in China. This was the first group of cadres sent abroad for long-term training, who later became key staff in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. To meet the demand for training a large number of cadres necessary for economic development and to reduce the cost of training in faraway countries, in 1951, the Vietnamese government reached an agreement with China to open two large training facilities in China for Vietnam: a campus in Nanning and a military academy for youth in Lushan³. Besides training civilian cadres, China also helped train and coach military officers. By June 1950, 3,100 Vietnamese cadres had gone to China for study, refresher courses at basic and intermediate levels, including junior infantry, artillery, and engineering officers (Military History Institute, 1994: 451). Commenting on Chinese aid to Vietnam, A. Patti, author of the book *Why Vietnam?*, wrote: “By 1950, Mao was in a position to assist Hồ Chí Minh through the northern border of Vietnam. Hồ was no longer isolated as before; he had many allies, first China and then the Soviet Union – a new playing field had begun” (Patti, 1995: 397).

From 1951 to 1953, Vietnam and China signed a series of economic and trade agreements: the Trade Agreement (April 1951); the Agreements on Commerce, Currency, and an Export Contract (May 1951); the publication of the “Trade Blacklist” (April 1952); among others.

During the years 1951 to 1953, China directly provided the most assistance, military aid, and war equipment to Vietnam. Specifically, in the years 1951-1952 alone, the value of economic aid China delivered to Vietnam amounted to 23,405 million VND. From July 1952 to January 1953, China took responsibility for training cadres, technical personnel, and soldiers for the 45th Regiment – the first heavy artillery regiment of the Vietnam People’s Army and the 367th

¹ The *History of Logistics of the Vietnam People’s Army (1944-1954)*, Volume 1 (General Department of Logistics, 1985, p. 146) offers detailed information regarding the types of aid received. Following the victory in the Border Campaign, the Vietnam-China border route was opened, allowing greater access to aid from fraternal countries. The aid primarily consisted of weapons and technical equipment. The military assistance included artillery such as 75mm DKZ guns, 90mm Bofors guns, K50 submachine guns, 7.9mm rifles, 12.8mm heavy machine guns, and mortars of 60mm, 81mm, and 82mm calibers. Regarding artillery, there were 75mm mountain guns, 105mm howitzers, and 37mm anti-aircraft guns. In addition to weaponry, allied countries provided materials, equipment, and machinery including propellant, explosives, detonators, cast iron, steel, copper, tin, lathes, milling machines, planers, generators, and various communication devices.

² International aid records, archived at the General Department of Logistics under files numbered 20 and 21, provide important documentation on the support received during the period (see also the Military History Institute’s *History of the Resistance War Against French Colonialism 1945-1954*, People’s Army Publishing House, Hanoi, 1994, Vol. 1, p. 542).

³ These two facilities later moved to Guilin and were not transferred back to Vietnam until 1955.

Anti-Aircraft Artillery Regiment. After six months of intensive training in Mông Tụ (Yunnan) and Tân Dương (Guangxi), and being fully equipped by China with Soviet weaponry, these two regiments returned to Vietnam to participate in combat during the Điện Biên Phủ campaign.

Between 1950 and 1954, the Chinese military advisory group working alongside the General Command of the Vietnam People's Army played a significant role, offering valuable recommendations for the operational activities of Vietnam's main forces on the main battlefield in northern Vietnam.

Out of a total of 50 major and minor campaigns, the Chinese military advisory group participated in seven campaigns⁴, directly assisting several key Vietnamese units in combat. "Most of the campaigns achieved victory, with some exceeding the planned objectives, such as the Border Campaign, but there were also campaigns that did not meet strategic requirements, like the three campaigns in early 1951" (Trung, 2009a)

The relationship between the Chinese advisors and Vietnamese commanders and soldiers was very good. General Võ Nguyên Giáp recalled: "In general, the relationship between us and the Chinese military advisors after the Border Campaign was excellent. Those friends helped us with their experience gained from the revolutionary war in China and the war against the U.S. in Korea" (Giáp, 1994: 23).

When working with the Chinese advisors, the Vietnamese side, from the General Command down to the corps level, respected and carefully studied the advisory opinions, especially those regarding the tactics of attacking fortified positions. However, at the same time, "the Central Military Commission and particularly Commander-in-Chief Võ Nguyên Giáp always based their decisions on the actual combat capabilities of their troops, adapting the advice and experiences of the Chinese comrades to fit Vietnam's real conditions to ensure certain victory while minimizing losses" (Trung, 2009a). By October 1954, there were 237 Chinese military advisors remaining in Vietnam, most of whom were staff working in support roles such as logistics, medical services, and communications. By August 1955, the advisory group was reduced to teams focused on logistics, politics, artillery, engineering, and civil aviation, with only a few dozen technical staff and advisors left. Following the directive from the central committee of the Communist Party of China to dissolve the advisory group, the personnel were withdrawn in three phases. Military experts and technical staff were invited to become specialists under the leadership of the Military Attaché Office (on a specialist basis). The Vietnamese Party and Government highly appreciated the contributions of the Chinese military advisory group. On the occasion of Vietnam's National Day on September 2, 1953, the Vietnamese Party and Government "awarded the Hero of the People's Armed Forces medal, the Emulation Soldier medal, and the Resistance Medal to more than 30 advisors and staff; at the same time, 397 advisory personnel were awarded commemorative resistance medals" (Trung, 2009a).

According to Chinese statistics, during the entire war against the French, China provided Vietnam with "155,000 firearms of various types, 57,850 rounds of ammunition, 3,692 artillery pieces, over 1,080,000 artillery shells, more than 840,000 grenades, 1,231 vehicles, over 1,400,000 sets of military uniforms, 14,000 tons of food and supplementary provisions, over 26,000 tons of fuel, and a large quantity of medicines and other military supplies" (Trung, 2009a). During the Điện Biên Phủ campaign, China provided comprehensive support to Vietnam, from ammunition to food supplies. Due to the urgent demands of the campaign, China supplied "1,700 tons of rice, accounting for 6.8% of the total rice mobilized for the campaign" (Trung, 2009a), and provided 3,600 rounds of 105mm artillery shells (these accompanied 24 artillery pieces sent from China to Vietnam from late 1953), which accounted for 18% of the total artillery ammunition used.

Additionally, after scavenging supplies from depots, China transferred 7,400 more rounds of 105mm shells to the Vietnamese People's Army, although 105mm artillery shells became scarce in China after the Korean War (due to difficult transportation conditions, the additional 7,400 rounds only arrived after the

⁴ These included the Border Campaign, Midlands Campaign, Route 18 Campaign, Hà – Nam – Ninh Campaign, Northwest Campaign, Upper Laos Campaign, and the Điện Biên Phủ Campaign (except for the Hòa Bình Campaign, where Chinese advisors did not participate but instead focused on political training in the Ba Bể, Bắc Cạn region).

battle had ended in May 1954.) In the final days of the Điện Biên Phủ campaign, China also helped equip a battalion of 75mm DKZ guns and a six-barrel rocket (Katyusha) battalion – the most powerful firepower the Vietnamese People’s Army had ever possessed at that time. These two battalions promptly participated in the final general offensive (May 6, 1954), firing a total of 1,136 rounds and playing an effective role in the campaign.

The Soviet Union’s Support for the Vietnamese People’s War against the French

Recognizing the support of the Soviet Union for the Democratic Republic of Vietnam as extremely important, shortly after gaining independence, the Indochinese Communist Party tried to establish contact with the Soviet Union but was unsuccessful. From 1947 to 1948, secret contacts began between the Soviet Union and official representatives of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam in Thailand and Paris. One important meeting between the Vietnamese side and the Soviet Union was between Phạm Ngọc Thạch and Soviet Ambassador Kolazhenkov in Switzerland (September 1947). According to Christopher E. Goscha, during the exchange, Phạm Ngọc Thạch skillfully explained to Kolazhenkov two issues that caused suspicion and misunderstandings among Soviet leaders about Vietnam’s situation: the dissolution of the Indochinese Communist Party (November 1945) and the Vietnamese leadership’s contact with Americans through the OSS organization. Overall, in these meetings, both sides mainly probed and sought to understand each other.

Although official diplomatic relations had not yet been established, the Soviet Union still provided financial assistance to the Vietnamese delegation in Bangkok and voiced support for Vietnam. The Soviet Union promoted the diplomatic activities of Hồ Chí Minh’s government and the Constitution of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam. The Soviet Union printed many publications about Indochina and Vietnam to help Soviet citizens better understand the history, land, people, and the heroic struggle of the Vietnamese people. When France launched its war to reoccupy Indochina and invaded Vietnam for the second time, the Soviet government opposed interference in Vietnam’s internal affairs, called for a solution to the conflict, and emphasized the urgent need to resolve colonial issues and establish an international supervisory regime... These unofficial activities had a certain effect on the progress of events in Indochina.

At the end of 1948, there was a new step forward in Soviet support for Vietnam: the Soviet Union proposed that the Asian-Pacific Economic Council meet the Democratic Republic of Vietnam’s government’s desire to admit Vietnam as a member (though the Soviet proposal was rejected by some countries). From 1948 until the establishment of official diplomatic relations between the two countries (1950), thanks to Soviet support, Vietnamese delegations expanded their ability to attend international conferences abroad and received support from some other people’s democratic countries. In 1950, the situation of the Vietnamese people’s war against French colonialists changed fundamentally in a positive direction, helping create the objective and subjective conditions necessary for requesting other countries to recognize and establish diplomatic relations with Vietnam. After establishing relations with China (January 18, 1950), on January 23, 1950, Foreign Minister Hoàng Minh Giám, on behalf of the Vietnamese government, sent a diplomatic note to the Soviet Foreign Minister, proposing that the two countries establish official diplomatic relations and exchange ambassadors.

To seek the Soviet Union’s support for the Vietnamese revolution, especially during the days when the recognition and establishment of bilateral relations between the Democratic Republic of Vietnam and the Soviet Socialist Federal Republic were being discussed, president Hồ Chí Minh asked Liu Shaoqi to convey to I.V. Stalin his intention to visit the Soviet Union. On February 7, 1950, Hồ Chí Minh sent a telegram explaining the secret intention of his trip to the Soviet Union: “First, in Vietnam, only a few central committee members and two government members know about my trip. Second, I think if the French know about my departure from Vietnam, they may take adverse political-military actions.”

Around mid-February 1950, Ho Chi Minh arrived in Moscow. The meeting between Ho Chi Minh and the leaders of the Soviet Party and Government did not take place at the Kremlin, as was customary for welcoming top state officials; it most likely occurred at a suburban villa called Kulsevo. Attending the meeting on the Soviet side were I.V. Stalin, V.M. Molotov, and several other Soviet Party and state leaders. Regarding the meeting's content, archival documents from both Vietnam and the Soviet Union remain classified and have not been fully released; therefore, reconstructing the details is extremely difficult. Most depictions are based on indirect information and secondary sources.

After recognizing and establishing diplomatic relations with Vietnam, the Soviet Union launched many activities to support the Vietnamese people's struggle for independence and freedom. In May 1950, at the National Congress of the Fighters for Peace and Freedom held in Paris, delegations from the Soviet Union (and Poland) and several other delegations agreed on a resolution demanding the French authorities end their aggressive war in Vietnam. In February 1951, at a meeting of the Committee on Industry and Trade of the Economic Council for Asia and the Far East, the Soviet Union once again fought for the Democratic Republic of Vietnam government to participate in the committee and proposed expelling representatives of the Bảo Đại government from this international economic organization. In February 1952, the Soviet Union rejected the Bảo Đại government's application to join the organization. In September 1952, at a regular meeting of the Security Council, the Soviet government representatives proposed reviewing the application and admitting Vietnam into the United Nations. When Britain, France, and the United States opposed this because Vietnam was not a recognized state, the Soviet Union asserted: currently in Vietnam, only Ho Chi Minh's government is the legitimate government, established by the National Assembly—resulting from free and secret ballot general elections on January 6, 1946—and recognized by the French government under the provisional agreement of March 6, 1946, unlike the Bảo Đại government which was propped up by France and the U.S.

Continuing to seek Soviet support and strengthen mutual understanding between the Vietnamese Workers' Party and the Soviet Communist Party, ahead of the 19th Congress of the Soviet Communist Party, Ho Chi Minh planned a second secret trip to the Soviet Union. On September 30, 1952, from Beijing, Ho Chi Minh sent a letter to I.V. Stalin presented his plan for a secret trip to the Soviet Union: "I very much wish to attend the 19th Congress of the Soviet Communist Party (b) (...) in Moscow... If I cannot attend the Congress, I still want to come to Moscow to inform and discuss with comrades some issues about the struggle in Vietnam and the Vietnamese Workers' Party." On October 1, 1952, I.V. Stalin sent a telegram agreeing to allow Ho Chi Minh to come to Moscow unofficially. However, Ho Chi Minh's trip was not as successful as hoped; the Soviet attitude toward Vietnam remained rather cautious. As someone who was wary of confident, independent leaders, Stalin saw Ho Chi Minh's successful leadership of the Vietnamese revolution as a challenge to be dealt with rather than supported. The lukewarm relationship at that time partly stemmed from "the Soviet leaders' desire for further proof of Ho Chi Minh's personal loyalty."

Although Vietnam–Soviet relations were not as close as Vietnam had hoped, since 1950 the Soviet Union had been providing Vietnam with significant military and economic aid. Soviet aid to Vietnam was non-repayable and usually exceeded Vietnam's requests. The first shipments included "37 mm anti-aircraft guns, some Motorola transport vehicles, and military medicines" (Giáp, 1995: 12) which passed through China before arriving in Vietnam. According to Vietnamese statistics, from May 1950 to June 1954, Vietnam received 21,517 tons of international aid worth 54 million rubles (Military History Institute , 1994: 308-309)⁵ from the Soviet Union, China, and other socialist countries; this included all 76 37-mm

⁵ In the book *History of the Resistance War Against French Colonialism 1945–1954* (Vietnam Institute of Military History, People's Army Publishing House, Hanoi, 1994, pp. 308–309), the converted value of the volume of aid into rubles shows some discrepancy: "According to statistics from the Vietnamese military logistics sector, international aid to the Vietnamese people from 1950 to 1954 in the form of weapons, military raw materials, fuel transportation, rice, food, military clothing, military medicine, communications equipment, and engineering supplies totaled 21,517 tons, valued at approximately 136 million yuan (equivalent to 30 million rubles)" [p. 308]. The book further details: "In particular: in 1950 — 3,983 tons; in 1951 — 6,086 tons; in 1952 — 2,156 tons; in 1953 — 4,400 tons; in 1954 (from January to June) — 4,892 tons. By category, this included: 4,253 tons of weapons and ammunition; 73 tons of military engineering supplies; 5,069 tons of transportation goods; 9,590

anti-aircraft guns, all Katyusha rocket launchers, all K50 submachine guns, and most of the 685 transport trucks out of a total of 745 supplied by the Soviet Union⁶. Twelve multiple-barrel Katyusha rocket launcher units provided by the Soviet Union played a crucial role in the victory at the historic Điện Biên Phủ campaign. In 1952, president Ho Chi Minh requested from I.V. Stalin “10 tons of quinine (antimalarial medicine) for the army and civilians, meaning 5 tons within six months,” and Stalin immediately ordered the urgent shipment of 5 tons to Vietnam.

That same year, Ho Chi Minh requested to send 50-100 Vietnamese students to study in the Soviet Union and made specific demands for weapons, including: “(a) 37 mm anti-aircraft guns for 4 regiments, totaling 144 guns, plus 10 ammunition loads per gun; (b) 76.2 mm field guns for 2 regiments, totaling 72 guns, plus 10 ammunition loads per gun; (c) 200 12.7 mm anti-aircraft guns, plus 10 ammunition loads per gun.” In general, the Soviet Union fully and promptly fulfilled Vietnam’s requests. During that difficult period, this aid was very important. Especially, the military aid from the Soviet Union created strong offensive capabilities and fast mobility for Vietnamese troops and played a crucial role in several major campaigns.

On September 28, 1953, the Soviet Union called on the concerned countries to organize an international conference aimed at reviewing and seeking measures to reduce tensions in the international situation, and to propose solutions to major issues directly affecting the situation in Southeast Asia and the Asia-Pacific region. At the end of 1953, a Foreign Ministers' Conference involving the Soviet Union, the United Kingdom, France, the United States, and China (the Berlin Conference) announced the convening of the Geneva Conference, to discuss solutions for the Korean issue and the restoration of peace in Indochina. On April 27, 1954, the UK and the US authorized France to meet with the Soviet Union to reach an agreement on the composition of the conference. In structuring the conference, the UK, France, and the US excluded the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, proposing instead a formula of five major powers along with Laos, Cambodia, and the Bảo Đại government. The Soviet Union, however, proposed a formula of five major powers and four concerned parties (Laos, Cambodia, the Bảo Đại government, and the Democratic Republic of Vietnam). In talks with French Foreign Minister Georges Bidault, Soviet Foreign Minister V.M. Molotov raised the issue: “*It is impossible to discuss the restoration of peace in Indochina without the presence of the concerned parties.*” The Soviet Union insisted that it would not accept the presence of associated national delegations unless the Democratic Republic of Vietnam participated, because, according to the Soviet interpretation, “the concerned countries in Indochina included the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, the puppet Bảo Đại government, Laos, and Cambodia” – as explained by the Soviets in a telegram to China on February 26, 1954. On May 2, 1954, due to the Soviet Union's firm stance, the UK, France, and the US were forced to accept the proposal. With the strong and effective support of the Soviet Union, Vietnam participated for the first time in a major international conference, even though it had not yet been diplomatically recognized by the UK, US, or France.

The historic Điện Biên Phủ Campaign ended in victory, the Geneva Accords were signed, and the nine-year-long resistance war against French colonial invasion concluded successfully. The Vietnamese people always express gratitude and remember the immense support and assistance from the Soviet Union and China in their cause of resistance and nation-building. That support was further carried forward during the 21-year resistance war against the United States.

tons of rice; 1,505 tons of military clothing; 157 tons of medical supplies; 200 tons of communications equipment; 40 tons of engineering supplies. Some main types of equipment included: 715 transport trucks; 24 105-mm cannons with 1,100 shells; 48 75-mm mountain guns with 32,484 shells; 76 37 mm anti-aircraft guns with 51,620 shells. ([57]) Among the weapons and equipment mentioned above, aside from transport trucks, anti-aircraft guns, six-barrel rocket launchers, and K50 submachine guns—which came from the Soviet Union and Eastern European socialist countries—the remaining infantry weapons, 105 mm and 75 mm cannons, and food supplies were provided by the Chinese government and people.

⁶ Document collection on the demand, receipt, and distribution of aid goods in 1952, 1953, and 1954, National Archives Center I, Prime Minister's Office files, storage unit 2167.

References

- General Department of Logistics. (1985). *The History of Logistics of the Vietnam People's Army (1944–1954)* (Vol. 1) [Lịch sử hậu cần QĐND Việt Nam (1944–1954), Vol. 1]. Hanoi: Author.
- Joyaux, F. (1981). *China and the resolution of the First Indochina War* [Trung Quốc và việc giải quyết cuộc kháng chiến Đông Dương lần thứ nhất]. Hanoi: Information and Theory Publishing House.
- Military History Institute. (1994). *History of the resistance war against French colonialism, 1945–1954* (Vol. 1) [Lịch sử kháng chiến chống Pháp 1945–1954, Vol. 1]. Hanoi: People's Army Publishing House.
- Ministry of National Defense, Department of Research. (n.d.). *Authentic records of the Chinese military advisory group assisting Vietnam against the French* [真实档案中国军事顾问团援越抗法]. Hanoi: Ministry of National Defense.
- Ministry of National Defense, Department of Research. (n.d.). *Research materials on China's relations with Vietnam, 1949–1979* (Unpublished typewritten manuscript, Vol. 1). Hanoi: Ministry of National Defense.
- Patti, A. (1995). *Why Vietnam?* [Tại sao là Việt Nam?]. Da Nang: Da Nang Publishing House.
- Trần, H. N., & Dương, D. D. (Trans., Ed.). (2002). *Authentic records of the Chinese military advisory group assisting Vietnam against the French* [真实档案：中国军事顾问团援越抗法] (Dương Danh Dy, Ed.). Beijing: Chinese Communist Party History Publishing House.
- Trần, T. T. (2009, May 2). *China's assistance to Vietnam during the resistance war against the French (Part I)*. *People's Army Newspaper*.
- Trần, T. T. (2009a, May 3). *China's assistance to Vietnam in the anti-French resistance (Part II)*. *People's Army Newspaper*.
- Võ, N. G. (1994). *Điện Biên Phủ*. Hanoi: Thế Giới Publishing House.
- Võ, N. G. (1995). *Fighting in the Encirclement* [Chiến đấu trong thế bao vây]. Hanoi: People's Army Publishing House.
- Võ, N. G. (1999). *The Road to Điện Biên Phủ* [Đường tới Điện Biên Phủ]. Hanoi: People's Army Publishing House.
- Võ, N. G. (2004). *Complete Memoirs* [Toàn tập hồi ký]. Hanoi: People's Army Publishing House.

